

ENHANCING CUSTOM CATALOGUE METADATA FOR INCREASED USER FUNCTIONALITY IN DIGITAL PRESERVATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract - Following the launch of HSBC's Preservica-based cloud system for archival metadata management, digital asset storage and digital preservation, numerous opportunities for metadata enhancement have been identified. The two innovative projects described in this paper have provided significant improvements and efficiencies in the targeted search of custom catalogue metadata, allowing archivists to more readily and easily identify specific records. In the first project, we describe a methodology for the creation and population of a 'Contains Digital Asset' metadata field that allows users to identify catalogue entries with digital files. In the second project, the titles of folders within a catalogue entry's archival hierarchy are made readily viewable and searchable through a custom metadata fragment, allowing users to narrow searches to particular branches of the archival tree and/or derive differentiating contextual information for catalogue entries displayed in search results.

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Extended Abstract

In 2022, HSBC embarked on a project to upgrade and migrate our legacy digital preservation system to the Preservica NGI cloud.[1] A key objective of this upgrade was to eliminate the need for a separate online cataloguing tool, seamlessly integrating descriptive metadata for both physical and digital

records, alongside digitized and born digital assets within a storage and preservation system.

Following the successful launch of this upgraded system, our team has continued to identify and develop additional new solutions to improve the efficiency and usability of the catalogue search function. In particular, we have sought to address two key limitations that currently exist within the NGI system with: metadata improvements to provide reliable distinction between catalogue entries containing digital assets vs those with no digital asset; and a new metadata fragment to provide full detail and searchability of a record's entire catalogue hierarchy.

These solutions are described here to share their wider benefits with all who use Preservica NGI for metadata management and digital preservation.

I. ENHANCEMENT PROJECT 1: IDENTIFYING FOLDERS CONTAINING DIGITAL ASSETS

Following the launch of the upgraded system, user feedback revealed that it was challenging to distinguish and identify those catalogue folders in the system that contained digital assets from those that did not. Most user interaction with the system is based on search and, when faced with a list of search results, there was no clear, reliable way for a user to tell which of those folders contained a digital asset. The only way to determine whether there was a

digital file associated with a catalogue entry was to click on each individual folder in a set of search results, one-by-one, to see if there was a file inside that folder.

Our team's solution involved first identifying and creating a list of all catalogue folders in our system that contained a digital asset. This was accomplished using the 'Search Within' function, narrowing the search results to only show assets, and then exporting lists of assets with specified metadata that included the 'Parent Ref' value for each asset. This ultimately provided us with a report of all ~200,000 assets in the system, alongside the unique reference number for each asset's parent folder. A list of folders that contained assets!

We then used a custom-designed Python script that makes bulk updates to HSBC metadata fields from an Excel spreadsheet input. The script allowed us to populate a newly-created metadata field called 'Contains Digital Asset' with 'Yes' values for all parent folders containing assets, which had been identified in the previous step.

We overcame several challenges in implementing this seemingly simple solution, including: 1) limits on metadata export from search results that meant multiple searches were required to generate a complete parent folder list; 2) the existence of assets within structural subfolders that required extra processes to ensure the associated catalogue entries containing these 'wrapper folders' were accurately updated; and 3) the ongoing requirement for manual edits to the 'Contains Digital Asset' field following new ingests or moves of assets into empty folders, as the 'Yes' value does not automatically update.

As a result of this project, users can now quickly and reliably narrow searches to find digital files associated with catalogue entries. (Fig. 1)

Title	Contains Digital Asset
Photograph of the 1923 Shanghai office	-
Photograph of the 1923 Shanghai office	-
Photograph of the 1923 Shanghai office	Yes
Photograph of the 1923 Shanghai office	-

Figure 1.

II. ENHANCEMENT PROJECT 2: BREADCRUMBS FRAGMENT

ISAD(G) standards emphasise the need for hierarchical arrangement from the general (higher levels) to the specific (lower levels), and value a lack of repetition between levels.[2] Currently, Preservica NGI does not reveal information about parent levels when viewing folder metadata in search. This means that lower-level catalogue entries cannot be assessed alongside correct contextual information. For example, a lower-level folder might be titled 'Branch photographs', but within the search results, there is no way to know the bank collection or branch to which those photographs belong.

As our solution, a new custom metadata fragment called 'Breadcrumbs' was implemented. The Breadcrumbs fragment was created, populated and added to existing catalogue folders using a custom Python script developed by Preservica. The script harvested Titles of all hierarchical parent folders for a given catalogue entry and populated the associated XML level fields in the Breadcrumbs fragment according to the 'Level' metadata field (Fonds, Sub Fonds, Sub Sub Fonds, Series, etc.) in the HSBC catalogue metadata.

We overcame numerous challenges in this project, including: 1) the script's handling of folder titles with formatting exceptions such as carriage returns; 2) the script's handling of folders with no 'Level' value in the HSBC metadata fragment; 3) ensuring that the Breadcrumbs fragment can be frequently updated to reflect relevant changes to the catalogue; and 4) a limitation in the Preservica NGI platform, as of June 2025, wherein the grid display only allows for display of fields from one custom metadata fragment at a time, meaning users cannot view both HSBC and Breadcrumbs metadata on one search results screen.

The results of this Breadcrumbs enhancement project have meant that users are now able to more easily view and search across contextual information about the archival hierarchy. By selecting these Breadcrumbs fields to appear in the custom search grid display, a user can immediately sort and view the higher-level folder titles associated with the archival hierarchy for their search results. This removes the ambiguity that previously existed when viewing lists of search results, and ensures that users can target only those results that are most relevant in their search; for example, a user can now easily

display the branch and parent bank to which the various 'Branch photographs' catalogue entries belong. (Fig. 2)

Title	Fonds	Sub Fonds
Branch photographs	HSBC Global Resourcing	Processing Centre: Guangzhou I
Branch photographs	HSBC Bank Argentina	Head office
Branch photographs	The Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation	-
Branch photographs	The Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation	Branches: UK, London
Branch photographs	The Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation	Branches: China, Wuhan, Hankou (Hankow)
Branch photographs	The Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation	Branches: Malaysia, Cameron Highlands
Branch photographs	The Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation	Branches: UK, London, Gerrard Street

Figure 2.

REFERENCES

[1] J. Mortlock, "Cloud-based holistic digital preservation," *Digital Preservation Coalition Awards 2024*.

[2] International Council on Archives, "ISAD(G): General International Standard Archival Description – Second edition." [online] Available: <https://www.ica.org/resource/isadg-general-international-standard-archival-description-second-edition/>

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